

Lineaments mapping and digital analysis using remote sensing and geographic information system (GIS) in Erusu-Akoko area of Akoko North-West, Southwest Nigeria

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Abstract: Lineament analysis constitutes an interesting approach in geological studies, and it is considered as a very important structural and geological indicator used to determine regional, local tectonic trends and fracture zones in the rocks. Lineament extraction from satellite data has been the most widely used application in geology with several techniques. This study was carried out to illustrate the application and importance of remote sensing and geographic information system (GIS) techniques for lineaments mapping and digital analysis. The study demonstrates the use of NigeriaSat-X imagery for mapping and analysis of lineaments in the Basement Complex region of Akoko North-West area of Ondo State, Nigeria. Digital image processing techniques involving linear/edge enhancements, pan-sharpening and principal component analysis (PCA) were applied on the image to enhance the edges of the linear features using ENVI 5.3. The enhanced image was visually interpreted through GIS operations for lineaments extraction through on-screen digitizing using ArcGIS 10.5. These extracted lineaments were statistically analyzed to determine their lengths and densities. The results obtained were used to generate a lineament density map, lineaments statistics, and rose diagram. The lineaments have minimum and maximum lengths of 619.20 m and 6,099.13 m, respectively, with a total length of 349,358.56 m and an average lengths of 1,647.92 m. The lineament/fracture analyses indicated that the area has several long and short fractures whose structural trends are mainly in the north-west and

south-east directions. These lineaments are relatively high in areas around the central and south-western parts of the study area, and relatively low in the other areas. The results show that the integration of remote sensing and GIS, as well as manual lineaments extraction techniques carried out on NigeriaSat-X satellite imagery, provides a powerful tool in lineaments mapping and digital analysis.

Keywords: Remote Sensing, Geographic Information System, Manual lineaments extraction, NigeriaSat-X, Akoko, Nigeria.

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1. Introduction

Remote sensing and Geographic Information System (GIS) have become main tools often employed in recent years to gather geoscientific data for both regional and small-scale investigations. These technologies have been widely used in a variety of academic disciplines, including geology, hydrogeology, mining exploration etc, as a result of the growing interest in these technologies^(1, 2). For the past two decades, geomorphology-related geologic features have been identified and mapped using satellite photography^(3, 4). Nevertheless, lineament mapping, a crucial component of structural geology, can be used to locate these geologic structures and disclose the architecture of the underlying rock basement. Lineament mapping is crucial to geological research, particularly in mining and oil exploration^(5, 6). Lineament also qualify as a hazard signal of mining potential due to their frequent localisation near a feature of mineralogical resources^(7, 8). Lineaments can be the expression of structural features such as joints, faults, bedding plains, shear zones, fractures, fold hinges, and foliation on the ground surface⁽⁷⁻¹⁰⁾. These features could be associated with geologic structures (faults, joints, fracture traces, and line weakness), geomorphic features (cliffs, structural ridges, terraces, and linear valleys), tonal difference (vegetation, soil wetness, and rock composite), and anthropogenic characteristics (roads, electric grids, railways etc.)^(11, 12). Due to the significant vegetation cover and the thick terrigenous materials recovery, conventional ground-based mapping techniques are difficult and time-consuming and therefore ineffective for structural geology studies of humid tropical environments, necessitating the use of satellite imagery^(13, 14). As a result, the efficiency of lineament extraction has effectively increased due to remote sensing and geographic information system (GIS) tools that offer a synoptic view of any specific area. Multispectral and high-resolution images have proven to be a powerful and accurate tool in demarcating structural discontinuities. In order to identify and extract the structural lineaments, a number of authors used multispectral satellite images including Landsat 7 (ETM+) and Landsat 8 (OLI/TIRS) and other types of multispectral satellite images⁽¹⁵⁻²²⁾. Lineament identification and extraction in remote sensing can be carried out through two approaches (i.e., manual extraction, which mainly depends on visual interpretation and general knowledge of the interpreter; and automatic lineament extraction using computer software and algorithms^(2, 23, 24)). In the manual lineaments extraction method, lineaments are extracted from a satellite image through visual interpretation⁽²⁾. These lineaments are typically depicted on satellite imagery as straight lines or “edges,”

which are always a result of tonal variations in the surface material. In order to join broken segments into longer lineaments, the user’s knowledge and experience are crucial in lineament identification. Several studies have been carried out to manually extract lineaments using filtering operation, PCA and other various kinds of enhancements techniques^(2, 13, 14, 25-28). Though there are various methods of satellite image enhancements for the purpose of manual lineaments extraction, this work considers Principal Components Analysis and Pan sharpening^(14, 28-30). The principal objective of this study is to use manual extraction techniques to extract lineaments from NigeriaSat-X satellite image for digital lineament analysis. However, the geospatial analysis performed by Geographic Information Systems (GIS) such as lineaments’ density, length, and orientation will contribute to understanding the relationship between the extracted lineaments and tectonic relationship of the lineaments and the structural elements in the study area.

2. Study Area

The study area lies approximately between latitudes 7° 30' & 7° 50' N and longitudes 5° 35' & 5° 60' E in Erusu Akoko area of Akoko north-west of southwest Nigeria as depicted in figure 1. The extent of the study area is about 543.54 Sq. Km. Geologically, the lithological units in the study area include migmatite, granite gneiss, quartzo-feldspathic gneiss, undifferentiated schist, pegmatite, porphyritic biotite and chanokitic rocks^(11, 31). The granitic rocks consist of quartz, feldspar and biotite and/or tourmaline. The ages of the granites ranges from lower to upper triassic while the metasedimentary is thought to be upper paleozoic⁽³²⁾.

Figure 1: Location map and NigeriaSat-X Image of the study area.

3. Materials and Methodologies

3.1. Data

The satellite images used in this study is NigeriaSat-X and it is composed of three spectral bands, with bands 1, 2 and 3 having a spatial resolution of 22 m. NigeriaSat-X was chosen for the investigation because it can discriminate between a wide range of characteristics using its spectral capabilities. The region under investigation was cut out of the larger

scene covering the area. The NigeriaSat-X has three spectral bands that are available in the following wavelength ranges: 0.52-0.62 μm (green), 0.63-0.69 μm (red), and 0.76-0.9 μm (NIR)⁽³³⁻³⁵⁾. These three bands can be compared to Landsat-7 bands 2, 3, and 4, which are excellent in extracting rock characteristics and geological formations. The NigeriaSat-X sensor, which exhibits higher spectral bands and spatial resolution, was employed in this research instead of the earlier Landsat TM, ETM, and ETM+ sensors. An image from NigeriaSat-X completely covering the research region acquired in 2011 was used. The information about the NigeriaSat-X data employed in the research is detailed in Table 1. The image is georeferenced to the Zone 31 North UTM coordinate system. The steps applied for the lineaments extraction and analysis is presented in figure 2.

Table 1. The band characteristics of NigeriaSat-X data used in this study

NigeriaSat-X Bands	Type of bands	Wavelength (μm)
Band 1	Green	0.52-0.62
Band 2	Red	0.63-0.69
Band 3	NIR	0.76-0.9

Figure 2: Flowchart shows steps of lineaments extraction and analysis

3.2. Processing

Digital image processing was described by⁽³⁶⁾ as a technique for manipulating images using computer software in addition to producing images with higher resolution. The image processing was carried out in this study as follows.

3.3. Image sharpening

In digital image processing, pan-sharpening has been shown in various studies to be an effective method for identifying, extracting, and demarcating lineaments^(7, 31, 37, 38). Numerous methods, including IHS (Intensity Hue Saturation), Brovey, and Gram-Schmidt pan-sharpening^(39, 40), in this study, the pan-sharpening was employed and was applied coupled with ENVI 5.3 software to NigeriaSat-X images.

3.4. Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

In geological research, the principal component analysis (PCA) which is a statistical technique that removes redundant data, eliminates noise, and enhances the targeted information in the image^(28-30, 41), has been demonstrated to be useful in lineament identification. Li⁽⁴²⁾ and Anifowose, et al.⁽⁴³⁾ analyzed five alternative enhancement methods (including average value of all bands, PCA, Band Ratios (BR), histogram equalization, and high pass filter) that were used by Oyawale et al.⁽⁴⁴⁾ and found that PCA was more effective at identifying lineaments. Principal component analysis (PCA) has been utilized by several authors to map lineaments^(12, 44, 45). In this research, PCA transformation was carried out by employing three NigeriaSat-X channels (band 1, 2, and 3). Each dataset's channels have the same resolution of 22 m. This operation was carried out using the ENVI 5.3 software, and the result revealed that PCA: band 1 have values that can see the earth properties in the research area more clearly (Figure 3).

	PCA Band	Maximum (Unit)	Minimum (Unit)	Standard deviation
	1	215	0	11.734
	2	35	228	7.439
	3	0	58	1.535

Figure 3. Characteristics of NigeriaSat-X after the application of PCA method

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Lineament extraction

In this study, lineaments were manually extracted using visual interpretation from the NigeriaSat-X satellite image after being subjected to pan-sharpening and principal component analysis. On the satellite images, lineaments often show as edges or straight lines, and they are always caused by tonal variations in the surface material. When connecting broken segments to generate larger lineaments, the user's knowledge and experience are very important for lineament identification⁽²⁶⁾. However, as already been indicated in the literature, a number of general characteristics that help to identify the lineaments can be taken into consideration. Topographic features including straight valleys, continuous scarps,

straight rock boundaries, predictable river offshoots, sharp tone differences, and vegetation alignment are considered. A continuous straight valley is the most helpful feature as a major identification criterion in image processing for lineaments because a satellite image lacks direct information on the local topography, according to Onibudo et al.⁽¹¹⁾. The resulting lineament map is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Lineament map of the study area obtained from NigeriaSat-X

4.2. Classification of the lineaments extraction

To ensure that the extracted data was accurate, reliable and reproducible it was compared with already existing geographical data, particularly the road network dataset. Figure 5 shows the extracted lineament compared with the existing road network in the study area. This indicated that road network was not considered as lineaments during the process of lineaments extraction.

Figure 5. Extracted lineaments compared with the road network in the study area

4.3. Lineaments statistics

According to the statistic, a total of 212 lineaments were extracted and the length values of the extracted lineaments range from 619.20 m to 6,099.13 m. The extracted lineaments have an average length of 1,647.92 m, a total length of 349,358.56 m and with the most abundant lineaments lengths between 0.62 km and 2 Km (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Basic statics of the lengths of the extracted lineaments

4.4. Accuracy assessment

4.4.1. Lineaments Density

A lineament density map is a classification map that shows information about lineaments concentration that are present in a given area⁽⁴⁶⁾. In order to analyze the lineaments' dispersion pattern, lineament density maps were generated for the extracted lineaments in this study. This task was carried out by applying the spatial analyst's line density tool in ArcGIS 10.5 software. On the maps, red denotes the highest density values, while green denotes the lowest values. The density was also used in this investigation to determine the distribution and concentration of lineaments (Figure 7). The lineaments extracted from the NigeriaSat-X image (Figure 4) present the high density values concentrated mainly in the central and southern parts of the image. Most of the lineaments are located near average and high density areas.

Figure 7. Density map of the extracted lineaments

4.4.2. Orientation

Orientation analysis of lineaments allows the identification of the most frequent directions of lineaments. Lineament orientation is analyzed by creating rose diagrams for the extracted lineament map, which allows highlighting the number of most frequent lineament in a particular direction. The directional rosettes are then produced with an angular spacing of 15° and without using the frequency. This procedure was executed with the aid of the Rockworks software. The rose diagram shows the orientations of lineament with the dominance of NW-SE direction (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Orientation and statistics of the extracted lineaments

5. Conclusion

The study has demonstrated the importance of lineament mapping and digital analysis of a typical basement terrain involving the integration of remote sensing and GIS techniques. This involved the interpretation and GIS analysis of NigeriaSat-X satellite data acquired for the year 2011 of 22 m spatial resolution for the lineament mapping and digital analysis of the extracted lineaments. The Image, after been subjected to image processing with pan-sharpening and principal component analysis (PCA), the comparison of the results obtained indicated that the best bands for this extraction is PCA band 1. This process was carried out in order to avoid noise affecting the results, and the principle component analysis was applied to remove the correlation between bands and to highlight the differences in hue and texture saturation of the image. This technique not only highlight the edges of linearity but also effectively reduced the noise. The results of the analyzed lineament/fracture indicated that the area has several long and short fractures whose structural trends are mainly in the north-west and south-east directions. The lineaments are relatively high in areas around the central and south-western parts of the study area, and relatively low in the other areas. However, the comparison of the extracted lineaments with the existing geospatial dataset, particularly the road network shows that the road network was not considered as part of the extracted lineaments. This validates the integration of Remote Sensing and GIS, as well as manual lineaments extraction techniques carried out on NigeriaSat-X satellite imagery, and provides a powerful tool in lineaments mapping and digital analysis.

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